

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 4 | OCTOBER - DECEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
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Volume I, Issue IV | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

VIRGENIA A. MANLUYAO

Instructor I

Jose Rizal Memorial State University – Dipolog

virgeniamanluyao@jrmsu.edu.ph

“THE WALLS”

In the raging storm, with shattered homes,
We cried for help in a desperate voice
For who would come to these lowly lands,
Who's not blind to see our ravaged ground?

But as we waited under weary stars,
Aidance came, we thought was scarce.

A man arrived, boldly he stood:
“Give ear!” said he, “I have a word.”

He claimed he heard our earnest prayer
Thereupon, he took this saving venture
He was “The One,” a name proclaimed,
Who would free us from catastrophe and shame.

For days, he tended to the crowd
Many believed his actions spoke aloud
For what we ate, where we slept, how we strived
He was there to help us stay alive.

Then he shouted the despair in his eyes:
The misery of people beneath stormy skies.
Hence, he promised a life better and just,
“The One will be back,” said he “In me, trust.”

Years passed, The One stayed in our minds and lips
Until he triumphed a high golden seat
He returned but declared a change of name
“Call me ‘The Elect,’ but sure, I am still the same.”

He vowed to help through an auspicious plot
But first, he needed all the coins we sought

Thus, we gave away all that we have
To a better life – a hope through the elected man.

We waited... but The Elect never returned.
So we went to that high place he had earned
But shocked we were, as walls were built
The Elect said it's to protect the coins he received.

Days and days, we worked so hard
To give the coins to his regard
But the more we gave, the walls climbed so high
Until he vanished completely from our sight.

He sent men to collect coins from our sweat
Now we toil like we are the ones in debt!
They asked from us, yet we look more like beggars
For who could fight against when they held the triggers?

Then another man came out of the blue
New name, old game – a pretentious view
He made a promise – as if this act is not new
Still the people honored him, believing him true.

And so, many walls arose from all the lies
Now we breathed and lived like a sacrifice
We have the power whom to believe, whom to select
Yet we end up compelled to serve The Elects.

Who can blame the people clinging to the smallest hope?
If it's the only thing they can hold – a chance to cope
If all deceive, should they just choose the lesser evil?
But how could this even matter,
If all the walls were never built for the people?

